

Improved DASH Video Streaming Performance by MEC-Enabled Optical Access

C. Centofanti, A. Marotta, C. Rinaldi, F. Franchi, D. Cassioli, and F. Graziosi
University of L'Aquila,
carlo.centofanti1@graduate.univaq.it
{andrea.marotta; claudia.rinaldi; fabio.franchi; dajana.cassioli;
fabio.graziosi}@univaq.it

Abstract: We discuss how different service placement can improve DASH performances on an edge-enabled architecture in a MEC infrastructure. Network experiments emulate a real optical network behaviour allowing to measure improvements with different service placement. © 2021 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

The growth of connection speed pulls for new network architectural models. One of the most promising technology is the so called Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) [1, 4] architecture, which enhances network performance by making storage and computation capacity available at the edge. The reduced physical distance between end users and service location drastically lowers the latency [7]. The MEC technology represents a viable solution also for video delivering, which is the most consistent portion of nowadays Internet traffic. By 2022, video related traffic will be 79% of the whole Mobile data traffic and 82% of all consumer traffic generated in Internet [2]. Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP (DASH) is an enabling technology to distribute video chunks with different quality formats, finding the best trade-off between audio/video quality, network conditions and user's requests. The DASH, in combination with the MEC technology, can effectively address network-related problems, like, e.g., bandwidth shortage and high latency. In this work, we evaluate the performance improvement provided by a MEC-enabled optical access network on video streaming DASH services with respect to conventional cloud-based architectures. We run controlled network experiments by reproducing a real optical access network. The quality of the video transmission experienced by the users is evaluated and compared under different MEC deployment configurations. Our study evidences the advantages of MEC deployment at the Optical Line Termination (OLT) compared to both the deployment at the customer premise and the traditional deployment in a cloud regional provider.

2. System Model

We consider the reference architecture shown in Fig. 1a, composed by a *network infrastructure* and a few *computing resources* managed by a service and orchestration layer. The network infrastructure consists in a Time Division Multiplexed Passive Optical Network (TDM-PON).

Fig. 1: (a) The network scenario: a MEC-enabled PON architecture; (b) Throughput distribution over 24 hours, one sample per minute

MEC architectures are based on two main pillars: *Multi-access* and *Edge Computing*. The *Multi-access* technology connects different network nodes belonging to different access networks, enhancing network performances in the context of regional services. The *Edge Computing* in MEC will drastically lower latency [7] by reducing the physical distance between the end users and the network nodes where the service is running so enabling vertical services with stringent latency requirements.

Three different scenarios are considered in our study, i.e.:

- **MEC at customer premise:** the MEC node is inside the customer network. This configuration achieves maximum throughput and minimum latency for the users.
- **MEC at OLT:** the MEC node is inside or directly connected to the Internet Service Provider (ISP) access network, i.e., the user shares the optical resources with other active users connected to the Passive Optical Network (PON). This may reduce the available bandwidth while achieving a latency slightly lower than 1 ms. Fig. 1 shows the 24-hours trace of available bandwidth collected from a real commercial Gigabit-capable Passive Optical Network (GPON).
- **MEC at Cloud:** The MEC node is deployed at the regional *Cloud*, outside the ISP network. This is the worst-case scenario, with a reduced bandwidth and a high Round Trip Time (RTT) in the range of tens of milliseconds.

The Service and Orchestration Layer shown in Fig. 1a is composed by the *MEC Platform Manager* and the *DASH Service Platform*.

The *MEC Platform Manager* shown in Fig. 1a provides an uniform Application Programming Interface (API) to the upper layers. Its functions include:

- **Lifecycle Management:** this process takes care of the entire MEC application lifecycle, treating each MEC application instance as a Virtualized Network Function instance
- **Policy Enforcement:** it manages networks and applications connectivity, according to the network policies
- **Inter-host Management:** this block is responsible of enabling networking and communications between different MEC hosts, exposing them to the *Service Layer*.

The *DASH Service Platform* handles the DASH service. The *MPEG-DASH* technique, provides adaptive bit rate streaming over simple Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) GET calls. Videos are parted into segments or chunks, with a fixed length in time and a fixed bit-rate. Each chunk reproduced by the player at the client side is characterized by a *Quality Index (QI)* associated to a video resolution and achieved bit rate. The QI assumed in our experiment span from 1 which is associated to a resolution of 320x180 px @254 Kbps up to 12 which corresponds to 3840x2160 px @30000 Kbps.

The client makes decisions about the quality of requested video chunks, by using an Adaptive Bit Rate (ABR) algorithm to monitor both the network parameters and the player status so optimizing the Quality of Experience (QoE) according to the current network conditions [3]. Several ABR algorithms have been proposed. The most relevant ones are *Bola* [6], and *Throughput*. *Bola* uses the buffer level indicator to estimate the best bit-rate for the next chunks. The *Throughput* algorithm bases its decisions upon the recent throughput history. We use a dynamic switch between those two to reach the best results [5].

3. Experiment Setup And Results

We set up three machine: a server, a gateway and a client. The server is responsible to store and serve the video content. The client continuously runs 5 parallel video playbacks for 24 hours. The gateway reproduces the network bandwidth and round trip time associated with the MEC scenarios described in Sec. 2, by running a *nodejs* daemon. The daemon fetches network data from our database and apply them to the network. For the purpose of our experiment, we use real data measured over a commercial GPON in the city of L'Aquila, Italy. The recorded network behaviour is then reproduced as follows: for the MEC at cloud scenario we apply recorded bandwidth and RTT; for the MEC at OLT we only apply bandwidth restriction; for the MEC at customer premise we consider 1 Gbps Ethernet connection.

Fig. 2a shows the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of experienced video *Quality Index*. As expected, the MEC at cloud scenario achieves the worst performance, due to higher latency and bandwidth limitations. This is explainable by the fact that the experienced throughput is inversely related to the RTT, which is maximum for this scenario, and at the same time is directly related to the available bandwidth. The MEC at OLT achieves comparable performance to the MEC at customer premise case which theoretically represents the best solution

Fig. 2: Results.

from the technical view point, achieving maximum bandwidth and minimum latency. This makes MEC at olt configuration an interesting compromise between costs of the infrastructure and performance.

By adopting the MEC at customer premise as the theoretically reachable target for the *Cloud* and *OLT MEC*, we define an *Average Penalty* metric to measure deviations from the adopted baseline. This allows to estimate the loss in terms of *Quality Index* drop. *Cloud* and *OLT MEC* average penalties are expressed as a percentage of the deviation from the baseline reference value. Fig. 2b shows that MEC at OLT performs 5% better with respect to the cloud case, in terms of QI.

4. Conclusion and future work

In this paper we have evaluated the impact of a MEC-enabled OLT in the context of DASH video streaming scenarios. The results show that with a Fiber To The Home (FTTH) GPON, it is possible to improve the overall video quality transmission placing a MEC node in the access network reducing RTT. Results show that the improvements given by the presence of MEC at OLT are comparable with the data obtained with the *MEC at Customer Premise* baseline. Comparing the OLT MEC with the *Cloud* the increase of *QI* indicator shows that it is possible to increase users QI placing resources into the optical access network. The *Cloud* performs significantly worse than the *MEC at Customer Premise* baseline. In future work we plan to investigate the impact of different ABR algorithms and PON dynamic bandwidth assignment strategies on the performance of MEC-based video delivery.

Acknowledgement

This work has been partially supported by the H2020-MSCA-RISE OPTIMIST project (GA: 872866) and by the Italian Government under CIPE resolution no. 135 (December 21, 2012), project INnovating City Planning through Information and Communication Technologies (INCIPICT).

References

1. MECISG ETSI. Multi-access edge computing (mec) framework and reference architecture. *ETSI GS MEC*, 3:V2, 2019.
2. GMDT Forecast. Cisco visual networking index: global mobile data traffic forecast update, 2017–2022. *Update*, 2017:2022, 2019.
3. DASH Industry Forum. Abr logic, 2021.
4. Quoc-Viet Pham et al. A survey of multi-access edge computing in 5g and beyond: Fundamentals, technology integration, and state-of-the-art. *IEEE Access*, 8:116974–117017, 2020.
5. Kevin Spiteri, Ramesh Sitaraman, and Daniel Sparacio. From theory to practice: Improving bitrate adaptation in the dash reference player. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications (TOMM)*, 15(2s):1–29, 2019.
6. Kevin Spiteri, Rahul Urgaonkar, and Ramesh K Sitaraman. Bola: Near-optimal bitrate adaptation for online videos. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, 28(4):1698–1711, 2020.
7. Jingjing Yao, Tao Han, and Nirwan Ansari. On mobile edge caching. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 21(3):2525–2553, 2019.